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BUSINESS EXCELLENCE: A RELECTION AND FURTHER DEVELOPMENT OF TQM

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ABSTRACT

Over the last few years, a paradigm of quality management has been successfully forged in our business world. Organizations worldwide have been exploring ways to improve business practices to gain competitive edge, which is at hard competition and globalization quality has become the necessity.

Our paper discuss the “hot topic” of Business Excellence (BE) aiming to highlight and clarify the connections with Total Quality Management (TQM). Thus, we describe the quality movement from inspection to statistical quality control and the “Japanese Age” of quality followed then by Total Quality Control (TQC) and TQM developments that derived to the models of BE. After that, we present some perspectives of defining the excellence and an overview of BE models with focus on the referential ones. Finally, it’s an attempt to draft the coordinates of the "journey" through TQM towards its excellence in Business.

Keywords: Organization; Quality, Excellence; Total Quality Management; Globalization; Business Excellence.

Introduction:

The business environment is becoming more and more complex day by day and the marketplace has changed from local to global and today this lead global market to compete with competition.

Thus, every market is becoming more aware of rising standards day by day, due to heavy access to wide range of products and services to choose from. The demand of quality products or services is ever-increasing and this global revolution had forced organizations to invest substantial resources in adopting and implementing quality management strategies which is been considered a key strategic factor in achieving business success i.e., QUALITY, which is more than ever required, and it has become the key slogan as organizations strive for

a competitive advantage in markets characterized by liberalization, globalization and knowledgeable customers.

Quality gurus such as Juran, Deming and Crosby have advocated various methodologies for business success and single out some quality practices. In order to respond to the highly competitive external environment, enterprises continuously search for new effective approaches to enhance their management capabilities such as Total Quality Management (TQM), Business Excellence Models (BEM), Business Process Reengineering (BPR), Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP), Organizational Change Management (OCM) etc. Among these various approaches TQM and Business Excellence Models have been among the most popular ones in the past two decades which has created a positive impact on business performance both in manufacturing and service sectors.

Thus, every customer is becoming more aware of rising standards day by day, due to heavy access to wide range of products and services to choose from. The demand of quality products or services is ever-increasing and this global revolution had forced organizations to invest substantial resources in adopting and implementing quality management strategies.

DEFINITION OF QUALITY

When the expression "quality" is used, we usually think terms of an excellent product or service that fulfills or exceeds our expectations. These expectations are based on the intended use and the selling price. For example, a customer expects a different performance from a plain steel washer that from a chrome-plated steel washer because they are a different grade. When a product surpasses our expectations we consider that quality. Thus, it is somewhat of an intangible based on perception. Quality can be quantified as equation as follows:

$$Q = P / E$$

Where Q = Quality

P = Performance

E = Expectations

If Q is greater than 1.0, then the customer has a good feeling about the product and service. Of course, the determination of P and E will most likely be based on perception with the organization determining performance and the customer determining expectations.

Where does the quality starts with and what dimensions to be considered to compete with uniqueness?

Quality starts with market research - to establish the true requirements for the Product or service and the true needs of the customers. However, for an organization to be really effective, quality must span all functions, all people, all departments and all activities and be a common language for improvement. The cooperation of everyone at every interface is necessary to achieve a total quality organization.

Overall, Quality has nine different dimensions, according to the study of Japanese analysis and these dimensions are somewhat independent; therefore, a product can be excellent in one dimension and average or poor in another. Very few, if any, products excel in all nine dimensions. Therefore, quality can be determined as standard by using a few of the dimensions of quality.

The Dimensions of quality as follows:

DIMENSIONS	MEANING AND EXAMPLE
Performance	Primary product characteristic such as the brightness of the picture
Features	Secondary characteristic added features
Conformance	Meeting specifications or industry standards, workmanship
Reliability	Consistency of performance over time, average time for the unit to fail
Durability	Useful life, includes repair
Service	Resolution of problems and complaints, ease of repair
Response	Human-to- human interface, such as the courtesy of the dealer
Aesthetics	Sensory characteristics, such as exterior finish
Reputation	Past performance and other intangibles, such as being ranked first

These dimensions help in identifying and marketing the product with their relative importance and later it is then translated into the requirements for the development of a new product or the improvement of an existing one.

Overall quality management represents a rebirth in organization management with an emphasis to gain a competitive advantage by providing quality products or services. A quality holds the key competitiveness in today's global market. In addition, the concept of TQM philosophy and its principles was introduced and this concept was primarily in response to

the severe competitive challenge from Japanese companies. TQM has widely considered as an effective management tool to provide business with stability, growth, and prosperity. Total quality management (TQM) has been recognized as one of the important issues and generated a substantial amount of interest. Thus, TQM has been regarded as one of effective ways for firms to improve their competitive advantage.

DEFINITION OF TOTAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT (TQM)

TQM can be defined as:

“A set of techniques and procedures used to reduce or eliminate variation from a production process or service-delivery system in order to improve efficiency, reliability, and quality”.

“TQM is an integrative philosophy of management for the continuous improvement of product and process quality in order to achieve customer satisfaction”.

COMPONENTS OF TQM:

TQM content as having four main components:

- Market advantage,
- Reliability,
- Design efficiency, and
- Process efficiency.

The first two allow firms to generate profits by increasing revenues, and the latter two increase profits by Cutting costs.

DRIVING FACTORS FOR TQM:

The factors which force the organization internally and externally to attain to compete are as follows:

- Customer Focus
- Management Leadership
- Human Resource
- Quality data and reporting
- Suppliers' Management
- Process Management

TQM process and Deming's 14 principles of quality management helped to improve productivity and performance of the organization, which lead to succeed, with all of the components within the organization which was collectively involved. The total quality movement has gone through many transformations and it focused on building total quality in every task that is performed in an organization. Quality has changed with the passage of time with changing customer's needs and requirements. Therefore, it was seen a dramatic shift in the total quality management focus from a concentration just on manufacturing, to a wide company spectrum of activities and, more specifically, to the needs of the internal and external customers.

The transformation from inspection mode to prevention mode is considered to be a very important step in building quality from the very beginning of the manufacturing process. The figure shows briefly the history of Total Quality Management (TQM), from inspection to Business Excellence.

Fig: TQM from inspection to Business Excellence

DEFINING “EXCELLENCE”

Even if we fail to highlight all facets of the complex concept of excellence, we propose to present some definitions, approaches and representations that have contributed to the "enrichment" of the concept of excellence and to the “shaping” of the concept of Business

Excellence. The starting point in achieving excellence is to improve quality. The natural sequence of steps to reach excellence is suggestive highlighted in Deming's chain (Figure 2).

Fig: Deming's chain

Excellence is the state or quality of excelling. Particularly in the field of business and organizations, excellence is considered to be an important value, and a goal to be pursued. Excellence is defined as: “the ability of firms to make profits, while meeting the customers’ requirements” which is represented in a triangular form in the so called “triangle of excellence”.

Fig: Triangle of excellence

The evaluation of excellence is done in the space delimited by the three axes. The arrows indicate the path of improvement measures to achieve excellence. Therefore, excellence means success in the competition by obtaining high quality products and services, offered to customers in shortest time, in terms of efficiency.

BUSINESS EXCELLENCE IS TQM?

Business Excellence is “excellence” in strategies, business practices, and stakeholder-related performance results that have been validated by assessments based on specific models proven

to support the challenging journey towards excellence. TQM models are often called Business Excellence Models. Also, TQM itself is now often called Business Excellence. This is to distinguish the “new” TQM from the past work on TQM. Business Excellence is really the same as TQM, but with a more clearly defined approach.

The first Business Excellence models were developed in the mid-1980s and came about as a result of the quality movement. Over time, the term “Business Excellence” started to replace the terms “Quality” and “TQM”, partly as a result of the before mentioned considerable confusion as to the meaning of TQM (since all types of business improvement programmes were being called TQM). Today, many countries view Business Excellence models as a key mechanism for improving the performance of organizations, as well as national competitiveness.

The most popular of these models are manifestations of principles of TQM implementation in the entire organization. By far the majority of organizations that use such a model do so for a self-assessment through they can identify improvement opportunities, areas of strengths, using the model as a framework for future organizational development. In the followings, we present an overview of some referential Business Excellence models.

The EFQM Model

The EFQM Excellence Model has recently been reviewed and revised so to align the framework with current business needs and trends. Used as a tool for assessment, it supports organizations in defining what sustainability means, providing approaches for its implementation and ensuring consistency between apparently conflicting responsibilities toward shareholders, employees and society.

The Baldrige Model

The Baldrige model provides a systems perspective for understanding performance management and reflects validated, leading-edge management practices against which an organization can measure itself. The Baldrige criteria represent a common language for communication among organizations for sharing best practices.

Fig: The Baldrige Model

The Australian model: Business Excellence Framework

The Australian model, named Business Excellence Framework (BEF) is defined as “an integrated leadership and management system that describes the elements essential to sustainable organizational excellence”.

BEF is based on enduring principles of organizational improvement that are interpreted according to individual business settings using seven ‘Categories’ and seventeen sub-categories, or ‘Items’. The seven business settings (Categories) are the following: information and knowledge; leadership; customer and market focus; strategy and planning; people; process management, improvement and innovation; success and sustainability.

The organization’s performance against each Category and Item is evaluated using the Assessment Matrix ADRI that shows the extent to which the organization’s systems and operations are aligned to the principles of Business Excellence.

Fig: Assessment Matrix-ADIR

Hence we can see that TQM philosophy-as a corporate strategy, and applying any model for Business Excellence for Strategy implementation can facilitate implementation as both are approaches require development of capacities for company-wide changes. Once individual and organizations develop elements of management like leadership, teamwork, stakeholder empowerment and involvement, resource allocation and measurement/metrics etc., the result is the creation of a mindset and approach, which can facilitate any future change management. This results in the formation of an Integrated Quality Loop. This loop comprises of individuals and teams who have the capacity to internalize the concept and view the entire business as a continuous quality loop, or process, with the customer as its initiator.

CONCLUSION

Total quality management (TQM) has been proposed to improve business performance and received considerable attention in recent researches. A growing number of organizations use quality management as a strategic foundation for generating a competitive advantage and improving firm performance. Firms that have won quality awards generally outperform other firms with respect to both income measures and stock market value.

Our paper synthesized the results of a literature review in the “hot topic” of excellence in business, thus joining various conceptual approaches and applicable models. By highlighting the connections between the referential concepts & models of BE and basic principles of TQM and how worldwide organizations should act to achieve it. In brief, on this general

direction, the paper argues that TQM is the *upshot* condition for any organization which targeting excellence in business.

As a final remark, we may consider our journey to achieve excellence in business as being just in progress. Therefore, it is very important for each of us to understand clearly that entering and maintaining in this twirl of never-ending quality improvement is a resultant of daily individual actions (starting with top managers and ending with bottom-line workers) and furthermore this is not a simply target but rather a continuous journey toward higher levels of organizational performance which imply a continuous process of quality improvement.

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